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Regio-selective synthesis of 5-substituted 1H-tetrazoles using ionic liquid [BMIM]N3 in solvent-free conditions: A click reaction

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Abstract

A multi-component, one pot and regio-selective synthesis of different 5-substituted 1H-tetrazoles was successfully accomplished via a click reaction. In this respect, we have performed the reaction of either isatins or various aromatic aldehydes with malononitrile and ionic liquid, 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium azide ([BMIM]N3), as a relatively green source of azide mediated by *o*-phthalimide-*N*-sulfonic acid (OPNSA). The calculated thermodynamic results demonstrate a reliable agreement with our experimentally observed regio-selectivity. From the electronic viewpoint, we have also assessed the nature of regio-selectivity via quantum theory of atoms in molecule analysis.

Keywords

5-Substituted 1H-tetrazoles, Click reaction, Density functional theory, Ionic liquid: 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium, azide, Quantum theory of atoms in molecule, Regio-selectivity, Liquids, Molecules, Quantum theory, Aromatic aldehyde, Malononitriles, Multicomponents, Quantum Theory of Atoms in Molecules, Regio-selective, Solvent free, conditions, Tetrazoles, Ionic liquids.